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Decision on Proposal Submission - Special Section on Variable Selection for Complex Psychometric Data

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2026年2月5日 1:56

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Cc: "Cho, Sun-Joo" <sj.cho@vanderbilt.edu>

Dear Ryuhei Ishibashi,

Thank you for submitting your proposal for the special section on “Variable Selection for Complex Psychometric Data” at Psychometrika. We appreciate the time and effort you invested in preparing the proposal. After careful consideration by the editorial team, we regret to inform you that we are not able to invite a full manuscript submission based on this proposal.

The proposal seeks to develop item selection indexes that address sensitivity to processing speed and time between learning and assessment. This potentially leads to improved intelligence assessments. There is not much information about how the indexes are defined, but the proposal gives us the impression that they are data summaries as opposed to modeling advances. Because of this and because there already exist IRT models to incorporate response times and longitudinal data, we do not think the Theory and Method section of Psychometrika is the best outlet for this work.

Due to the large number of proposals received and the limited space available in the special section, we could encourage only a small proportion to proceed to full submission. In addition, given the special section’s focus, we prioritized proposals with a clear and distinct methodological contribution aligned with the aims of the call.

Thank you again for considering Psychometrika for your work.

Best wishes,

Guest Editors

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